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Guidebook on inclusive, participatory and resilient sustainable urban food sharing scenario planning D 4.2

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1. INTRODUCTION

Food systems and urbanisation processes are at the heart of current environmental and social challenges, positioning cities as pivotal in advancing food systems transformations (HLPE, 2024). Amidst the growing uncertainties of climate and ecological crises, deepening social inequalities, and shifting societal values, the need for innovative, forward-looking tools and methodologies is more urgent than ever. This guidebook introduces one such approach: scenario planning tailored to urban food sharing.

Futures thinking—also known as futuring—offers powerful tools to understand the complexity of food systems and imagine transformative pathways. Scenario planning, in particular, enables diverse stakeholders to explore possibilities, surface tensions, and collaboratively shape more inclusive and sustainable futures. By integrating diverse perspectives, these exercises encourage collaborative decision-making and challenge prevailing narratives. Policymakers, stakeholders in the private sector, and civil society actors can harness these methodologies to anticipate actions that yield desirable outcomes, explore multiple sustainability pathways, and engage more reflexively with future possibilities.

This guidebook has been developed within the context of CULTIVATE, a four-year research project funded by Horizon Europe designed to support sustainable urban and peri-urban (UPU) food sharing and help transform urban food systems onto more just and sustainable pathways. CULTIVATE includes a range of collaborative activities with multiple actors to enhance, evaluate, support, and scale sustainable food sharing initiatives across Europe. CULTIVATE's mission encompasses research and innovation aimed at unveiling the dynamics that foster or hinder food sharing practices, among others by co-producing knowledge on how to transform governance dynamics in order to promote sustainable food sharing.

Building on recent developments in futures literature and exercises (see section 4), particularly in the urban food and food sharing domain (Hebinck et al., 2022; Fitzgerald & Davies, 2022, 2024), we designed a methodology to support inclusive, participatory, and resilient urban food sharing. The methodology included three phases, each using different tools (see Table 1):

- Phase 0 focused on ensuring the co-design of the process and its relevance for the local context;
- Phase 1 where participants develop collectively a vision for the future as well as transition pathways to attain it through back casting techniques; and,
- Phase 2 when transition pathways are subjected to a stress test under diverse plausible and locally relevant futures to create resilient plans.

Phases	Tools
Phase 0: Co-designing the workshop: make them relevant to your city	<p>Define the topic and Framing question</p> <p>Stakeholder selection</p> <p>Survey on perceived enablers and barriers</p>
Phase 1: Visioning and transition pathways development	<p>Visioning: Develop a collective vision for the future</p> <p>Backcasting: Develop the initial transition pathways</p>
Phase 2: Stress testing the transition pathways	<p>Local Exploratory Scenarios: Adapt explorative scenarios to the local context</p> <p>Stress Test: Revise, adapt, and improve initial transition pathways under local explorative scenarios to make them resilient.</p>

Table 1 - Phases and tools

This methodology was applied and refined through a series of workshops conducted in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht. These experiences allowed us to explore the role of scenario planning as a catalyst for enhancing food sharing in urban contexts. This guidebook encapsulates the insights gained from these interactions, providing readers a detailed guide to conducting scenario planning workshops, fostering collaboration and driving positive change.

Whether you are a researcher, policymaker, or practitioner, this guidebook equips you with tools to co-create more equitable, resilient, and sustainable food futures. Our aim is to support the formation of diverse alliances, uncover opportunities for innovation, and turn collective visions into actionable plans. Together, we can reimagine the future of food sharing and contribute to a more equitable and resilient food system for all.

2. STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO ORGANISING SCENARIO PLANNING WORKSHOPS

This section presents all the steps necessary for developing the scenario planning workshops. What follows is a detailed description based on the application of this methodology in Barcelona, Milan and Utrecht as part of the CULTIVATE project.

Figure 1 summarises the overall process.

Figure 1: Explanatory roadmap of the scenario planning workshop

2.1. Phase 0: Co-designing the workshop: making them relevant to your city

Planning carefully scenario workshops is crucial for anticipating potential challenges and opportunities throughout the whole process. Some of the key elements that will need to be taken into consideration are embedding the workshops in relevant city's processes or dynamics, the selection of participants, venue and logistics, timing and roles, and the coordination of the facilitation team. Commitment to inclusiveness is crucial to involve effectively food-sharing stakeholders in developing resilient solutions for building a more sustainable food system. Organisers should prioritise inclusiveness a guiding principle from the very beginning. Creating resilient and sustainable food systems depends on engaging a broad range of voices —particularly those often excluded from formal planning processes.

Considering Inclusivity Participatory Scenario Planning Workshops

Scenario workshops intended to support inclusive, participatory, and resilient urban food systems must be designed with attention to **what** the workshop addresses, **who** is involved, and **how** the process is structured and facilitated. Inclusivity is not simply a matter of representation—it involves engaging with deeper issues of power, access, and recognition. This requires planning across **preparation, during, and post-workshop** phases, with a clear understanding of both the **potential** and **limitations** of participatory processes. The following guidance outlines key considerations which, on many occasions, are challenging to adhere to fully, but they provide pointers to embed inclusivity as a strategic and ethical commitment throughout the entire process. It is important to note that the design and facilitation of scenario workshops must be flexible and sensitive to local dynamics, recognizing that the **most meaningful form of inclusion may vary** depending on the context, stakeholders, and specific dynamics of the transition being addressed.

1. What – Framing the Workshop Content

- The workshop should **explore content that resonates with diverse groups** and food system actors, including those typically excluded from formal decision-making. This for example includes giving space to addressing issues from an everyday experience perspective (such as individual food access challenges) to structural inequalities.
- Workshop themes must reflect the **tensions between inclusivity and transition dynamics**. Food system transitions often involve conflict and trade-offs—decisions to include some voices can result in the exclusion of others. These

tensions must be openly acknowledged and considered in the preparation and framing the workshop.

- Prioritize **equal recognition of all types of knowledge**—from scientific, formal expertise to local, lived, informal, and tacit knowledge. This recognition is foundational across all phases.
- Clearly communicate the **transparency of the process**, including how decisions will be made, what the outcomes are intended to be, and how participant input will be mobilised.

2. Who – Participant Selection and Engagement

- **Ensure participation across a wide range of food system actors and diversity of backgrounds**, with specific attention to marginalized and structurally excluded groups. Consider diversity in socio-demographic and economic backgrounds (such as gender, age, and cultural identity). Avoid tokenistic inclusion by engaging early and meaningfully. If regularly excluded groups are difficult to engage, reflect on the implications of who is participating and not for the outcomes of the process.
- Address **accessibility systematically**—including cost, time, language, mobility, digital access, and caregiving responsibilities. Participation must not require disproportionate effort or resources from those already disadvantaged.
- Facilitate **access to the necessary resources** that allow all participants to actively contribute—this includes logistical support, background materials, and interpretation.
- Create a **safe space** that fosters trust and encourages honest communication. This starts in the pre-workshop phase, through transparent outreach, and continues during the workshop with clear ground rules and respectful facilitation.

3. How – Workshop Design and Facilitation

- **Facilitation** must ensure **equal power within the process**, through inclusive methods that actively manage dynamics of dominance and silence. You can also include awareness-raising prompts early in the workshop to make visible the power relations, exclusions, and systemic inequities within food systems.
- Alternate between **individual reflection, small group, and plenary discussions**. This allows participants to prepare thoughts, hear from others, and engage meaningfully across formats.
- Provide **adequate information** in accessible formats to enable all participants to deliberate meaningfully. This supports genuine freedom to express views without fear or disadvantage. For example, using visual aids.
- Build **authenticity and accountability** by ensuring facilitators and organizers are clear about what influence the workshop outcomes will have, and by following up with concrete actions.
- Include **feedback loops** during and after the workshop to keep participants informed of how their contributions are being used, and what decisions or changes result.

There are trade-offs in the process and many challenges to ensure inclusivity in participatory process; it is key to be aware of your choices and purposefully reflect on how to ensure more equitable spaces in terms of participation.

For more information and reflections on inclusion see

Giesbers, E., Mattijssen, T. J., & Leeuwis, C. (2025). Citizen participation in food systems transitions: How inclusive should it be?. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 56, 100986.

Karen Bell, Mark Reed, The tree of participation: a new model for inclusive decision-making, *Community Development Journal*, Volume 57, Issue 4, October 2022, Pages 595–614, <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsab018>

Zaremba, H.; Elias, M.; Devi, J.T.; Priyadarshini, P. (2021) Inclusive participatory approaches: A facilitator's guide. Rome (Italy): Bioversity International. 24 p. ISBN: 978-92-9255-234-3

Box 1: Considering Inclusivity Participatory Scenario Planning Workshops

2.1.1. Choosing the Topic and Framing the Question

At the heart of a successful scenario planning workshop lies a clearly defined topic and a well-framed guiding question. **The focus of the scenario planning workshops is to bring together different actors to explore how food sharing initiatives can deliver greater sustainability benefits.** Participants typically include individuals from government, businesses, and food sharing organisations who come together to discuss a specific food-related issue. Organisers must select a topic for the workshops and formulate a question to guide the discussions. To ensure relevance and depth, organisers should consult with potential participants and local experts to better understand the key debates, recent developments, and pressing challenges in their specific food system context. This co-creative process helps shape a guiding question grounded in local realities and aligned with existing concerns and aspirations. A well-crafted question will serve as a focal point throughout the workshop, anchoring discussions and helping participants identify the most impactful issues.

In the case of our hub city examples, the design of these workshops was informed by the governance landscape analysis of Milan (Matteini et al., 2024), Utrecht (Medema et al., 2024), and Barcelona (Herrero et al., 2024). CULTIVATE conducted a detailed analysis of the community-based urban agriculture, food waste recovery and redistribution and social and solidarity economy governance landscape for each hub city. While not a mandatory step for replicating the scenario planning process, this contextual analysis supported the development of the workshops, identifying the key barriers and enablers affecting food sharing initiatives in the different locations. Drawing on existing studies, local diagnoses, or ongoing processes—such as urban food strategies—can similarly help refine the workshop’s focus and ensure it aligns with the city’s specific challenges and opportunities.

In **Barcelona**, organisers initially explored the possibility of organising planning scenarios in collaboration with the City Council, focusing on the social and solidarity-based food distribution sector. However, over time, the emphasis shifted toward food waste and redistribution. Reaching consensus on the final topic and guiding question required time, dialogue, and negotiation among a diverse group of local stakeholders. Following consultations with organisations active in this field, the framing question was defined as:

How should we approach, plan, and organise the double challenge of preventing food waste and loss while granting, at the same time, the right to healthy food in the metropolitan region of Barcelona by 2040?

In **Milan**, the municipality was a main organiser and the framing question was defined as:

What would I like the food waste situation to look like in Milan by 2040?

In **Utrecht**, the question was developed in close consultation with the local municipality. Drawing on insights from the previous governance analysis, the organising team identified a key challenge: the fragmentation of food sharing governance across multiple municipal departments. In response, the workshop aimed to convene stakeholders from diverse domains—such as public health, social cohesion, climate action, and circular economy—to explore opportunities for future collaboration. Accordingly, the question was framed in a relatively open fashion:

How can we create a future-proof, healthy and inclusive food environment in Utrecht together?

2.1.2. Selecting Participants

The selection and invitation of participants is a crucial step in the process of organising the scenario planning workshops. **The success of these workshops depends heavily on participants' commitment to both the process and its outcomes.** To ensure meaningful contributions and active engagement, it is important to strike a balance between diversity and manageability. Limiting the number of participants to between 20 and 25 allows for rich dialogue while maintaining an inclusive range of perspectives.

Organisers should begin by developing a list of potential participants and prioritising invitations based on clear criteria (see Box 1 above for a deeper reflexion on inclusivity). **Selection should aim to ensure representation across key sectors**—including the public sector, private sector, and civil society—as well as **diversity in socio-demographic backgrounds** (such as gender, age, and cultural identity). It is equally important to include individuals with **varied areas of expertise and experience**, particularly those working with different social groups or across different dimensions of the food system.

Organisers can compare their initial list of potential participants with a qualified individual in the relevant field to help complete the map of key stakeholders. For example, the municipal Food Policy Office of **Milan** helped organisers in reviewing the list of participants and recommending additional key stakeholders.

Once the invitations are sent, the organisers must follow up to confirm attendance. This includes sending reminders, asking for confirmations, and potentially inviting additional participants (if some invited people rejected their invitation) to maintain the desired number and diversity of attendees. At this stage, it is important to clearly communicate the expectation that participants attend both workshops, as their continued involvement is key to ensuring consistency, continuity, and meaningful engagement throughout the process.

2.1.3. Venue and Logistics

Before the scenario workshops, organisers need to visit the venue in person. This allows them to visualise how the activities will unfold in the specific space, assess the layout, and identify any logistical needs—such as materials, equipment, or signage—that may be required on the day of the event.

Choosing an appealing and contextually relevant venue can also enhance participants' engagement and set a positive tone for the workshop. For example, the

first workshop in Utrecht was held at an urban care farm, which created a pleasant atmosphere and sparked participants' imagination when envisioning food futures.

If visual documentation is desired, organisers may also consider hiring an illustrator or visual facilitator to capture key moments, ideas, and outcomes throughout the workshop.

In Barcelona, organisers hired an illustrator who combined drawings and text to visually summarise key insights from the workshop. The illustrator also created tarot-inspired scenario planning cards, designed to enhance engagement and creativity in future workshops (see Annex 1).

Additionally, completing Table 2—which outlines the step-by-step structure of the event—can be highly beneficial. This table provides a clear overview of the workshop sequence and helps identify who is responsible for each task. For reference, Annex 2 includes an example of how this table was completed for the first scenario planning workshops in Barcelona.

DURATION	TIME	WHERE	BLOCK	ACTION	WHO DOES IT	MATERIAL NEEDS/WHO PROVIDES	COMMENTS

Table 2 - Organisation table

2.1.4. Timing and Roles

The organisers must design a detailed timetable for the scenario planning workshops and share it with the participants in advance. The schedule should include arrival times, breaks, and sufficient time for informal interactions, as these workshops also serve as valuable networking opportunities for individuals working on related topics who may not yet know each other. The scenario planning workshops outlined in this guide consist of two phases, namely (1) Visioning and transition pathways development, and (2) Stress testing the transition pathways.

Each phase consists of two core exercises that participants are expected to complete. These two phases can be conducted in a single day (with a break) or split into two half-day sessions. Tables 3 and 4 provide sample timetables from the workshops held in Barcelona, offering guidance on how to structure each phase effectively.

Time	Activity	Grouping	Outcome
15	Welcoming coffee/tea		
30	Introductions and questionnaire insights, methods	Plenary	Participants and facilitators get to know each other. Organisers present contextual insights and introduce the day's activities.
60	Working Groups: Visioning	Groups of roughly 5/7 people	Visualise desirable future and identify specific goals for backcasting in the next activity.
30	Sharing the Visioning	Plenary	We share what the groups have done to unify a joint vision for all.
15	Coffee Break		
60	Backcasting	Groups of roughly five people	Develop a step-by-step action plan for achieving specific goals that are part of the vision by working backwards from the future vision to the present.
15	Feedback and close	Plenary	Participants share the transition pathway

Table 3 – The timetable for Barcelona's Phase One.

Time	Activity	Grouping	Outcome
15	Welcoming coffee/tea		
30	Re-connecting with Phase 1 and presentation of scenarios.	Plenary	Presentation of an overview of the results of Phase 1, including an overview of the common vision and the scenarios that will be used for this phase.
45	Working Groups: Downscaling European Scenarios	Three groups of roughly 5 - 7 people, one scenario per group.	Grounding scenarios into the topic and local context: narratives storylines describing and grounding the story's development.
15	Scenario presentation	Plenary	One person in each group presents the narrative of their scenario
15	Coffee Break		
45	Working Groups: Stress testing and second backcasting in the context of each scenario	Same groups than first backcasting (Phase 1) than the first backcasting during the Phase 1	Each scenario group tests the back-casted plans developed in the previous Phase in the context of each scenario, resulting in the development of multiple alternative transition pathways.
30	Sharing the transition pathways	Plenary	One person from each group presents the insights of the exercise.
15	Wrap up and close	Plenary	The facilitator wraps up and closes the session

Table 4 - The timetable for Barcelona's Phase Two.

Organisers must define and assign various roles for future scenario planning workshops.

The main roles and associated tasks are described in the following table:

Role	Task	Description
Supervise all the organisation of the event	Coordinator	They need to be on top of the event and know everything that needs to happen.
Provide tea/coffee at the beginning/during the break	Catering service	They provide the drinks/food at the event. It is important to consider the space where this will take place and the disruption it may have on the general timing of the event and adjust accordingly.
Welcome, guide, and assist the attendants with the registration	Welcome assistant	They need to welcome, guide, and assist attendants during registration. They provide stickers for names and consent forms for image and recording rights.
Assist during the workshops with technical or logistical issues	Logistical or technical person	They need to be ready to assist throughout the process, whether sending the invitations, rearranging the space, or providing additional materials for the working groups.
Facilitate all the plenaries	One general facilitator	They need to welcome the participants, know the workshop context, explain the plan for the day, and guide them during the plenaries.
Facilitate group exercises	Four group facilitators	They need to facilitate the different group exercises.
Take photographs	Photographer	They need to photograph participants during the workshop, as well as their visual production.
Draw workshop	Illustrator	They need to draw the participants during the workshop
Control time during all the sessions	Timekeeper	They need to be aware of the time and warn 5 minutes before the end of each exercise.
Take minutes & write a feedback report	Secretary	They need to take minutes during the workshops (or listen to the recordings) and write the feedback report.

Table 5- Roles and tasks.

2.1.5. Coordinating the facilitation team

The scenario planning workshops involve several facilitators, who may be part of the organising team or/and hired specifically for the event. Before each workshop, it is essential to hold at least one meeting to ensure that all facilitators are familiar with the agenda and know how to facilitate each of the exercises during the two phases,

as well as their specific roles. It may be helpful to consider establishing a joint communication structure to improve coordination.

In **Barcelona**, a group of facilitators (some from the organising team and some explicitly hired for the workshops) met online twice before each phase and coordinated through a WhatsApp group.

2.2. Phase 1: Visioning and transition pathways development

Phase One marks the foundation of the scenario planning process. It invites participants to step into a creative and collaborative space where they co-develop a shared vision for a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient food future. This phase encourages participants to imagine what success could look like and to identify the concrete steps needed to achieve that desired future.

The process begins with individual and group visioning exercises, where participants articulate their aspirations and collectively define common goals. Building on this, the *backcasting* method is used to map out the transition pathways—working backward from the envisioned future to determine the key actions, enabling conditions, and milestones required along the way.

This phase is not only about generating ideas, but also about aligning diverse perspectives, fostering mutual understanding, and laying the groundwork for strategic planning. It helps ensure that the scenarios developed in later phases are grounded in collectively defined priorities.

2.2.1. Preparatory Activities

2.2.1.1. *Defining Working Groups for Visioning and the Backcasting*

The exercises developed in this phase require dividing participants into smaller working groups. Therefore, organisers should carefully plan group composition for both the **visioning** and **backcasting** exercises. The participants in each exercise may differ, and thoughtful group allocation is key to fostering meaningful dialogue and balanced contributions. For the **visioning exercise**, group formation should consider the following criteria:

- **Stakeholder diversity**, avoid placing participants from the same organisation in the same group to encourage cross-sector exchange.
- **Inclusion**, ensure representation that reflects diversity in age, gender, ethnicity, and other relevant social dimensions.

- **Approach diversity**, ensure representation from the public and private sectors, as well as food-sharing initiatives and civil society actors to include stakeholders with differing perspectives.

Once the visioning exercise is completed in smaller groups, the **backcasting** exercise can follow with new groupings formed based on participants' interests, motivations, or areas of expertise. Therefore, it is not necessary to pre-assign groups for the second exercise.

2.2.1.2. Preliminary Questionnaire

To prepare for Phase One, it is highly recommended that participants receive a preliminary questionnaire in advance. Their responses can provide valuable **context for the visioning exercise** by highlighting key insights and concerns. The questionnaire should aim to identify the main barriers, enablers, and priority action areas related to the selected topic.

In **Barcelona** and **Milan**, the questionnaire focused on two main areas: first, identifying the barriers and enablers to achieving food security for all and reducing food waste; and second, pinpointing key priority areas for intervention.

- What are the main barriers for [*your geographical working scale*] to deliver food security for all and reduce food waste?
- What are the main enablers for [*your geographical working scale*] to deliver food security for all and reduce food waste?
- What are the main areas where civil society, the public, and the private sector should concentrate on contributing to food security and food waste reduction in [*your geographical working scale*]?

2.2.2. Opening remarks

The opening of a workshop is a pivotal moment to engage participants, spark motivation, and communicate the significance of the process. Beyond thanking attendees for their time and contributions, organisers should clearly articulate the workshop's objectives and situate it within the broader local context. Sharing an analysis of the questionnaire results at this stage can help focus the discussion, highlight key themes, and acknowledge the diversity of perspectives and priorities present in the room—laying the foundation for meaningful dialogue. It is also important to provide a clear overview of the day's agenda and activities to set expectations and foster a sense of shared purpose.

In **Barcelona**, the organisers categorised the questionnaire responses according to whether they referred to the system, regulations, practices and information, or collaboration, organisation and management (see Figure 2).

Results from the questionnaire - OBSTACLES

- **System**
 - Structural aspects of the food system: agro-industrial, maximum profit, waste, long and unequal chains, generation of impoverishment.
 - Accelerated life without time
 - The polycrisis that the productive sector is suffering does not facilitate its action.
 - An increase in prices and the cost of living (energy, housing, etc.) destabilise budgets to combat poverty.
 - Food environments that do not guarantee food accessibility
- **Practices and information**
 - Fear and lack of information, insecurity
 - Lack of awareness among both citizens and collective operators (catering, collective canteens, etc.), to generate management systems that reduce waste. There is not enough awareness (production and final consumer).
 - Need to review commercial discard criteria.
 - Lack of data and information: Identification of the SA problem and its causes, confirming levels of food poverty and an insufficient diet, assessing the effect of the money card, How to measure? Difficulties in assessing the impact.
- **Regulation**
 - Lack of sufficient binding incentives.
 - Not enforcing the waste law (development of regulations and more inspections)
 - Avoid political decisions without consensus, strategies with Foundations and NGOs
- **Collaboration, organisation and management**
 - Lack of organisation and tools for collective procurement and redistribution of value and affordable prices
 - The elimination of European FEAD funds puts the survival of some social entities dedicated to food recovery at risk. The Barcelona City Council needs this network to guarantee food for people in vulnerable situations.
 - Collective mechanisms for food recovery are lacking.
 - Improve logistical efficiency, decentralise it to make it more accessible to regional entities, reducing warehouse and transport costs.
 - Define the MISSION clearly and ally us all (work with a network of well-coordinated social entities).
 - More volunteers are needed in addition to the employees who work
 - Well-coordinated social entities, food recipients to serve vulnerable people derived from social services and some of the support for job and social integration that is coordinated with food banks

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Figure 2: Example of how results from the questionnaire were categorised and presented during the opening of Phase One in Barcelona.

In **Utrecht**, responses from the questionnaire were grouped by theme and synthesised into key topics. These were printed on small cards, with different colours used to distinguish between enablers and barriers. Each card also featured anonymised participant quotes. These visual prompts served as effective conversation starters during the first workshop, helping to ground discussions in participants' real experiences and perspectives (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Example of quotes from the questionnaire printed for the Utrecht workshop.

2.2.3. Exercise 1.1: Visioning

2.2.3.1. Working Groups: Harvesting Individual Visions

The visioning exercise is a creative and collaborative process, requiring participants to collectively imagine and articulate a desired future related to the workshop's core topic for a specific year. For the workshops organised in Milan, Barcelona and Utrecht it was the year 2040.

In **Utrecht**, a guided visualisation exercise was integrated into the workshop programme. The facilitator led participants through an embodied imaginative activity, inviting them to take two physical steps forward—symbolically stepping into the year 2040—to envision the future food system. Participants were then

prompted to “look back” and reflect on the actions that had led to this envisioned future. This individual visualisation helped ground participants in the moment and connect them to their own imagination, providing a reflective starting point before sharing their ideas more succinctly within their groups.

Facilitators can emphasise that this exercise offers participants a chance to project their hopes onto a specific future timeline —encouraging them to imagine an ideal or “best-case” scenario.

To support the process, the following steps can be followed:

1. **Individual Reflection** – Each participant is asked to **reflect independently on their vision for the selected topic** (e.g., food waste and redistribution), writing their ideas on Post-it notes. Facilitators can stimulate thinking by posing guiding questions, drawing inspiration from the questionnaire responses.
2. **Sharing and Clustering** – Participants share their Post-it notes within their group. Facilitators help cluster similar ideas into overarching themes or “vision elements.”
3. **Group Discussion** – Group members engage in a collaborative discussion to explore the meaning behind their contributions, build consensus, and deepen their collective understanding of the envisioned future.
4. **Identifying Key Themes and Goals** – Each group synthesises their discussion by identifying the primary themes and associated goals that emerge from their shared vision.

In **Barcelona** and **Milan**, the guiding questions were:

- How would you like to envision food waste management in households, restaurants, the hospitality sector, and agricultural fields?
- How would you like regulations to evolve regarding food management?
- What are your thoughts on how the right to food may develop in the coming years?
- How do you imagine the interaction between granting the right to food and reducing food waste and food loss?

See Figure 4 for a visual summary of the visioning exercise discussions held in Barcelona.

Figure 4: Visual summary of the shared vision developed in Barcelona.

2.2.3.1. First Plenary: Clustering and Developing the Collective Vision

Following the visioning exercise, all participants reconvene in a plenary session to build a shared vision. Each group presents its envisioned future, allowing others to respond, enrich, or challenge the ideas presented. The organisers then collect and categorise the visions into thematic clusters (see Figures 5 and 6).

Once all goals have been grouped and the categorisations discussed with participants, everyone is invited to vote—using, for instance, stickers—on the four themes they consider most relevant. The top four clusters with the highest number of votes will form the basis for the subsequent backcasting exercise. Any points of disagreement or debate will be noted.

Participants are then reorganised into new groups for the backcasting phase. This time, they can choose which group to join based on their expertise, interest, or preferred theme.

TIP: If one group has too few participants during the second exercise, organisers can invite others to voluntarily join and help balance group sizes. Ensure that at least one person in each group has strong synthesis skills and relevant knowledge to support effective discussion and clustering.

TIP: Place voting stickers on participants' name tags in advance so they are easily accessible when it's time to vote.

Figure 5: The collective Vision developed in Milan with the individual visions clustered. Participants voted with the small post-its (blue: FSIs, orange: Researchers; Yellow: Public Administration).

Figure 6: The collective Vision developed in Barcelona with the individual visions clustered. Participants voted with the stickers.

2.2.4. Exercise 1.2: Backcasting

2.2.4.1. Working Groups: Develop the Transition Pathway Drafts

Backcasting is a structured approach that begins with a desirable future—referred to in this workshop as *the common vision*—and works backward to identify the steps needed to move from the present to that future. At each stage, participants ask: “If we want to achieve this step, what must be in place to make it possible?” This question is asked iteratively, moving step by step until reaching the current situation. This method mirrors how people often plan in everyday life. For example, someone aiming to be at work by 9:00 AM might realise they need to catch the 8:30 bus, which means leaving home at 8:00, finishing breakfast by 7:30, and being out of the shower by 7:00. This backward reasoning helps translate long-term goals into actionable steps—a relatable example that facilitators can use to effectively introduce the exercise (Vervoord et al., 2016).

For the activity, participants choose one of the four working groups, each focused on a key goal identified during the visioning session. Within these groups, they will collaboratively develop a backcasting roadmap to outline the actions and conditions required to realise the selected future vision. Facilitators will guide participants by presenting three questions related to three specific categories, as illustrated in Figure 7. These questions include:

- What needs to happen? - ACTIONS
- Who needs to lead this action? Who needs to collaborate to make it effective? - ACTORS
- What else is needed for the action to happen? - RESOURCES, DISCOURSES, PROCESSES...

Figure 7: The template for the backcasting exercise.

TIP: Organisers can bring a large white sheet with the backcasting template drawn for each of the four working groups, allowing participants to write or add Post-its directly onto the template. This helps structure participants' ideas and keep the conversation on topic (Figures 8, 9 and 10).

Figure 8: The backcasting exercise in Utrecht.

Figure 9: The result of the backcasting exercise in Milan.

Figure 10: The result of the backcasting exercise in Barcelona.

Figure 11 provides a visual summary of the backcasting exercise carried out by all working groups during the Barcelona workshop.

Figure 11: Visual summary of the backcasting exercise in Barcelona for all the working groups.

2.2.4.2. Plenary: Sharing the Transition Pathway Drafts

At the close of Phase One, organisers should create **space for participants to reflect on the day's activities, synthesise key insights, and consolidate what they have learned**. This moment also serves to acknowledge participants' contributions and efforts, while reinforcing the value of their input. Organisers should use this opportunity to introduce the focus of the upcoming workshop (Phase Two) and explain how the outcomes of Phase One will directly inform and shape that next step. If Phase Two is scheduled for a different day, it's important to let participants know that a summary of the workshop, including key results and next steps, will be shared with them in the interim.

TIP: In Utrecht, each group got time to share their future vision. This enabled cross-fertilisation and it energised participants for collective action.

If Phases One and Two are scheduled on the same day, it is beneficial to include a meal or extended break after the conclusion of Phase One. This not only provides an opportunity for informal networking among participants but also allows organisers time to review and synthesise the information gathered before proceeding to the next phase.

2.2.5. Elaborating and sharing the results: Vision and Transition Pathways

After Phase One, organisers should synthesise the information gathered during the workshop and compile it into a summary document. This document should capture the key insights from both the visioning and backcasting exercises. To support this process, it is recommended to use the template provided in Table 6. The template helps organise the agreed-upon vision, the sub-objectives identified to achieve that vision, and the specific steps required to reach each sub-objective. A separate table should be completed for each theme addressed during the second part of Phase One.

GOAL:				
Sub-Goals	Sub-Goal 1	Sub-Goal 2	Sub-Goal 3	Sub-Goal...
Step 1				
Step 2				
Step 3				
Step 4				
Step 5				
Step 6				
Step 7				
Step ...				

Table 2 - Template of the table needed to process information after Phase 1.

Once completed, this table becomes a central tool for guiding the activities in Phase Two. In Utrecht, for example, the table was printed in A1 format and used as a working document to revise and update the transition pathways during the stress-testing exercise. For reference, Annex 3 provides an example of how the table was filled out in Barcelona for the theme “*universalisation of food recovery.*”

The vision and corresponding transition pathways should be shared with participants after the workshop to invite comments or feedback. If Phases One and Two are held on separate days, organisers should also circulate workshop minutes. These should include a list of participants, a summary of the methodology used, and an overview of the key outcomes from the sessions.

2.3 Phase 2: Stress testing the transition pathways

This phase uses exploratory scenarios to stress-test the transition pathways developed in Phase One, assessing their ability to support the collective vision for 2040. Exploratory scenarios are not plans; they provide diverse contexts to aid decision-making. On their own, they do not offer a specific direction for action. Consequently, exploratory scenarios are often used to evaluate and inform the feasibility of plans. If a plan or policy is deemed feasible across a variety of challenging future scenarios, it can be considered robust.

Phase Two of the local scenario-guided transition pathways process is conducted in two stages:

- The first part of Phase Two focuses on **downscaling European scenarios**—specifically, those developed within the TRANSMANGO project (see methodological section)—to make them relevant to the local context. This involves adapting broad, European-level narratives to reflect the specific conditions, dynamics, and challenges of each participating city. Particular attention is given to key variables likely to influence the selected topic or project goals in the future.
- The second part involves **stress testing** the transition pathways developed in Phase One. Participants assess whether the actions and steps they previously identified remain feasible across the range of exploratory scenarios. They are encouraged to reflect critically on how each scenario might affect their strategy, and to consider what adaptive measures could be introduced to ensure the overarching goals can still be achieved, even under shifting or challenging conditions.

2.3.1. Preparatory Activities

Before launching Phase Two of the local scenario-guided transition pathways process, the organising team must carry out several preparatory tasks to ensure a smooth and meaningful workshop experience. These include:

- **Selecting key contextual variables** that are relevant to the workshop's topic and local dynamics. These variables will help ground the exploratory scenarios in the realities of the city or region.
- **Choosing the set of plausible future scenarios** to be used in the workshop. In our case, scenarios were selected from the TRANSMANGO project (Deppermann et al., 2015, pp. 14–15). Each scenario set includes four distinct narratives, designed to represent diverse combinations of key

variables. Ideally, the full set of four scenarios should be used to expose participants to a wide range of potential futures. However, adjustments can be made based on the number of participants and the time available for the session.

- **Assigning which plausible scenarios will be downscaled** and which ones will be later used to reflect on the initial transition pathways. This therefore includes assigning scenarios to working groups.

2.3.1.1. Preparing a relevant list of variables linked to the topic discussed

To begin the process of adapting the scenarios to the local context, organisers should prepare a list of key variables relevant to the specific city or topic. This list will serve as a starting point for collective discussion during the workshop. It can draw on insights gathered from the pre-workshop questionnaire, particularly the barriers and enablers identified by participants in relation to the focal area. These variables form the foundation for collaboratively developing locally grounded versions of the broader European scenarios.

2.3.1.2 Selecting Plausible Scenarios

Before conducting the Phase Two workshops, organisers must determine which plausible scenarios will be used. In our case, we selected a set of **TRANSMANGO scenarios** (see also Section 4 Methodological note). These scenarios were developed through a combination of research and participatory processes aimed at exploring potential future changes in European food systems. While designed at the European scale, they can be effectively adapted for use at the local level to support the development of robust and resilient transition pathways (see Vervoort et al., 2016). This process included the identification of eight key factors considered the most important and uncertain in the future of European food systems:

- Consumption patterns
- Environmental degradation
- Poverty and economic inequality
- Social and technical innovation
- Urban and rural population dynamics
- Power and market concentration
- Trade agreements
- Basic resource availability (water, energy, raw materials)

Stakeholders identified multiple possible states for each factor, along with their plausible combinations. These were processed using specialised scenario-building software to generate two distinct sets of four scenarios, each designed to maximise internal diversity. The resulting eight **TRANSMANGO scenarios** (see Annex 4) present eight possible future configurations of European food systems, each described through a concise narrative that outlines the state of and relationships between eight critical dimensions (Deppermann et al., 2016; Vervoort et al., 2016a). Table 7 presents the four narratives from the first scenario set, along with key trends for selected dimensions.

Fed up Europe	Fed Up Europe is a story of inertia in the food system under global pressures. Practices and business models leading to unhealthy diets and negative environmental impacts continue. The power of EU and national policy makers to change these trends decreases over time with a combination of decreasing funds and decreasing popular support. There is a lack of leadership in the face of climate and migration crises. Consumers' incomes are enough to avoid food insecurity, but many lack the knowledge, incentives or budgets for healthy life styles. In governments and in the private sector, there are minorities interested in changing the trend, but they are fighting an uphill battle.
Retrotopia	In Retrotopia, waves of immigration, terrorist threats and increasing impacts of climate change trigger social movements and policies that aim to keep global problems out of Europe, along with a nostalgia fueled sense of natural heritage and rural custodianship. Racism becomes more accepted; migrants are kept out, creating employment problems in greying societies, which are partly solved by robotisation of work; fear of migration from Europe's southern to northern countries due to climate change prompts European policymakers to help make Mediterranean countries more climate-resilient. Environmental 15 concerns drive down consumption of animal products; otherwise, the improvement of diets is not a priority amid concerns of European security and self-reliance
The Protein Union	The Protein Union is a story of a highly proactive response by the EU and its Member States, led by governments but supported by the private sector and civil society, to the challenge of changing European diets and modes of production. The focus is on creating new sources of protein, including mainstreaming insect consumption and the production of artificial quasi-meats, supported by new, more integrated means of food production and processing, at the expense of the livelihoods of smaller farmers. This is combined with strong action on reducing sugar closer to 2050, which nevertheless cannot avoid the legacy of unhealthier diets in earlier times.
The Price of Health	The Price of Health is a story that sees many Europeans returning to rural lives, out of necessity due to global pressures, because of changing social norms, and facilitated by technological advances in communications. These changes are supported by strong

	government policies regarding self-reliance and sustainability. Not everyone, however, is happy to be returning to the land – and the wealthiest do not have to follow suit.
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Table 3 - Four of the European Future Scenarios narrative. Source: (Deppermann et al. 2015, pp.14-15)

Organisers can build on the TRANSMANGO scenarios or draw from other existing plausible future scenarios. It is important to carefully select the specific scenarios to be used in the workshop. To ensure a meaningful stress-testing process and enhance the resilience of proposed strategies, a minimum of three distinct scenarios should be included. This allows participants to examine their goals across a range of contrasting future contexts.

TIP: When selecting scenarios, consider which ones might present the greatest challenges to a particular vision.

Organisers in **Barcelona** and **Utrecht** selected the “Fed Up Europe”, “Retrotopia” and “The Price of Health”, while in **Milan** they selected “Fed Up Europe”, “The Protein Union” and “The Price of Health”.

2.3.1.3. Assigning Scenarios to the Transition Pathways

Organisers must assign specific transition pathways to one or more scenarios for the stress-testing exercise. We recommend assigning **at least two scenarios per group**, as this allows participants to compare a wider range of opportunities and constraints, ultimately encouraging the development of more adaptable and resilient plans.

However, the approach can be adjusted based on the context. For example, in Utrecht, organisers chose to assign **one scenario per transition pathway** to reduce complexity and allow participants to explore a single transition in greater depth.

2.3.1.4. Defining Working Groups for Downscaling and Stress testing

In the first exercise of Phase Two, participants will divide into groups of approximately five to six people. These groups should be assigned in advance by the organising team, using similar criteria to those applied in Phase One (see Section

2.2.1), with a focus on **stakeholder diversity, inclusiveness, and diversity of perspectives**.

The groups formed for the stress-testing exercise can either be the same ones that developed the initial transition pathways or those involved in downscaling the scenarios—depending on what best supports continuity and depth of discussion.

2.3.2. Opening

The opening of Phase Two serves to recap the overarching goals of the scenario planning process, summarise the work completed so far—including the visioning and transition pathways—and provide a clear explanation of the step-by-step activities planned for this phase.

In **Barcelona**, there was a seven-week gap between Phase One and Phase Two, while in **Utrecht** and **Milan**, the workshops were held one month apart. To maintain continuity, organisers sent participants a summary of the first workshop in advance and revisited the collective visions during the opening of the second session as a refresher. Visual materials, such as illustrations of the visions developed, proved especially helpful in re-engaging participants and setting the stage for the next phase of work.

TIP: When the same participants attend both workshops, less time is needed for introductions during the second session. Instead, it becomes more important to allocate time for a meaningful and well-structured closing. This allows participants to reflect on the overall process, consolidate insights, and discuss next steps.

Organisers can also use visual materials to make future scenarios more accessible and engaging for participants.

In **Utrecht**, organisers created simple collages to represent each scenario, which were introduced at the start of the workshop (see Figure 12). These visuals helped participants quickly grasp key elements of the scenarios. To increase relatability, newspaper-style headlines were added to reflect trends already emerging in the present. However, be mindful that referencing current events may anchor thinking too much in the present and limit participants' ability to imagine more distant or less probable futures.

TOEKOMSTIGE SCENARIO:

RETROTOPIA

Figure 12: Collage created as a reference for the "Retrotopia" scenario.

2.3.3. Exercise 2.1: Developing Local Explorative Scenarios

2.3.3.1. Working Groups: Downscaling the Scenarios to the Local Context

This stage focuses on immersing participants in the exploratory scenarios. Participants are divided into groups, with each group assigned a specific scenario to explore in depth. The group facilitator distributes printed copies of the assigned scenario along with a list of predefined variables to guide the localisation process (see Section 2.3.1).

Each participant begins by reading the scenario individually and reflecting in silence. They are asked to consider how the scenario's end state might manifest in the local context, noting their thoughts in writing. This individual reflection phase ensures that all participants have space to form their own interpretations before entering group discussion.

Once everyone has completed their reflections, participants take turns sharing their ideas. The group then engages in a collective discussion to synthesise these perspectives and co-create a locally grounded narrative that captures the essence of the scenario in their specific city or region.

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While the scenarios are adapted from a local perspective, they are not limited to strictly local contexts. Any contextual factors—local, national, or global—that are relevant to exploring the transition pathways should be considered and integrated. As part of the exercise, each group is also encouraged to give their scenario a title, which helps to capture its core narrative and make it more memorable.

The outcome of this activity is a detailed, locally grounded narrative of the downscaled scenario, along with a meaningful and evocative title. Table 8 presents the scenario titles developed in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht for each of the original European scenarios.

SCENARIO	Barcelona	Milan	Utrecht
Fed up Europe	<i>An indigestible reality</i>	<i>Milan Works and Produces Food</i>	<i>Fastfood Property</i> (a wordplay in Dutch: FastFood Vastgoed)
Retrotopia	<i>Technoenvironment at all costs</i>	--	<i>Utrecht as a Fortress City</i>
The Protein Union	--	<i>The Big Brother of Food</i>	--
The Price of Health	<i>Urban dystopia vs rural "utopia"</i>	<i>Sovereignty and Monopolism between Self-Reliance and Global Corporations</i>	<i>Back to the Future</i> And <i>Climate-friendly future Utrecht</i> (this scenario was downscaled by two groups)

Table 8 - The scenarios' titles developed in Barcelona, Milan and Utrecht.

In **Barcelona**, the European scenario *Fed Up Europe* was downscaled to the local scenario titled “**An Indigestible Reality**”, accompanied by the following narrative (see Figure 13):

In Catalonia's peri-urban and rural areas, small and medium-sized farms have declined sharply, leading to the collapse of primary sector organisations. In response to ongoing severe droughts, there has been a dramatic increase in the import and use of chemical inputs such as fertilisers, herbicides, and pesticides.

At the same time, consumption patterns have shifted: local fresh produce is consumed less, while reliance on processed and imported foods is rising. These trends have driven up food prices, triggering population movements. Many have left the increasingly industrialised and inhospitable countryside for urban areas—only to find cities themselves strained by supply issues, prompting some to leave in search of more stable living conditions. The small-scale farms that endure focus primarily on self-sufficiency. Any surplus production is distributed through limited, community-based marketing networks. Rising fresh food prices have also led to more efficient use of food, resulting in a notable reduction in waste.

In this scenario, the market for sustainably produced food splits along two lines: one serves affluent consumers who can afford premium prices, while the other caters to marginalised, cooperative-based rural communities. These so-called “**shelters**” are formed largely by younger generations disillusioned with the collapse of the welfare systems their parents once depended on. Rooted in values of eco-social awareness and mutual care, shelters operate on principles of self-sufficiency and exchange economies—though they remain a small fraction of the overall population.

At the policy level, social, educational, and healthcare services have been drastically rolled back, with the latter two sectors largely privatised. This, coupled with increased consumption of unhealthy, ultra-processed foods, has contributed to a steep decline in public health, reducing life expectancy to just 60 years. Environmental regulations have also regressed, legitimising the widespread use of high-impact chemicals and reinforcing the dominance of industrial agriculture.

Additionally, during this period of decline, laws and regulations concerning food waste have been revoked. The era is also characterised by increasing immigration and intercultural interaction, which, unfortunately, has led to heightened social tensions as communities compete for increasingly scarce food aid resources. Finally, growing economic insecurity has contributed to the expansion of so-called “canyoning areas” in the city's peripheral zones—spaces marked by severe deprivation and deteriorating public health conditions.

Figure 13 provides a visual summary of all the downgraded scenarios in Barcelona. Figures 14 and 15 provide insights into the downgraded scenarios in Milan and Utrecht.

Figure 13: Visual summary of the downscaled scenarios in Barcelona

Figure 14: The result of the downscaling of the TRANSMANGO scenario "The Price of Health" called "Sovereignty and Monopolism between Self-Reliance and Global Corporations" in Milan.

Figure 15: The result of the downscaling of the TRANSMANGO scenario "The Price of Health" called "Back to the Future" in Utrecht.

2.3.3.2. Plenary: Presenting the local explorative scenarios

At the end of the exercise, all groups reconvene in a plenary session. Facilitators, together with participants, present the titles and narratives of the locally adapted scenarios developed during the group work.

2.3.4. Exercise 2.2: Stress Testing Transition Pathways

2.3.4.1. Working Groups: Adapting Transition Pathways Under the Local Explorative Scenarios

Participants are divided into groups as determined during the preparation of Phase Two. Each group is assigned a transition pathway to stress-test under one—or ideally two—local scenarios. The process begins with the first scenario and is then repeated with the second.

To start, participants spend 5–10 minutes immersing themselves in the assigned local scenario by reading its detailed description individually. After this silent reading, they are invited to share reflections or questions within their group. Some participants may have been involved in creating the scenario and can help clarify uncertainties, or the group can reach out to another team responsible for its development.

Next, participants review the transition pathway they developed in Phase One, beginning with the overarching goal that emerged from the shared vision. They then examine the associated sub-goals and specific steps, including proposed actions, responsible actors, and required resources. To support this process, each group is provided with a printed version of their transition pathway, formatted as a table (see Table 6).

Working through one scenario at a time, the group critically analyses their pathway, assessing its feasibility and identifying where adjustments may be needed in light of the contextual challenges presented by the scenario. For each milestone in each plan, participants address the following questions:

- 1. Would the proposed action be effective in this scenario?*
- 2. What barriers could obstruct the successful completion of this action in the scenario?*
- 3. What positive factors or enablers might exist in the scenario that could help achieve the action?*

Participants may choose to retain, modify, clarify, or add actions to their transition pathways to ensure alignment with their vision under each scenario. As they work through the stress-testing process, they annotate the printed transition pathway tables with their reflections and adjustments (see Figures 16 and 17). Figure 18 offers a visual summary of how the stress-testing process unfolded in Barcelona.

TIP: Organisers can print large-format versions of the backcasting templates for each of the four working groups, allowing participants to write directly on them or

add Post-its during the stress-testing exercise. For example, in Utrecht, participants used orange Post-its to highlight barriers and green ones to indicate positive factors or enablers. This hands-on approach helps make the process more interactive and visually engaging.

Figure 16: The result of the stress testing exercise in Barcelona.

Figure 17: The result of the stress testing exercise in Utrecht.

Figure 18: Visual summary of the stress testing process in Barcelona

2.3.4.2. Plenary: Sharing the Results of the Stress-test Process

After working in groups, participants reconvene in a plenary session to present the key outcomes of their stress-testing process. This involves outlining the new actions developed to achieve the goal under various scenarios, along with identifying the stakeholders who should participate in implementing those actions.

It is important to close the workshop with a clear and thoughtful summary of the main achievements and outputs. This final session should also include time for collecting participant feedback and outlining the next steps in the process to maintain momentum and ensure continued engagement.

During the closing session, it is key to **provide space and encouragement for participants to share their reflections, insights, and potential takeaways from the workshops**. This moment not only fosters meaningful dialogue but also helps participants begin identifying actionable steps that are relevant to their local contexts.

The closing should be facilitated with care—participants should not feel pressured to take on responsibilities, but opportunities to build on the momentum of the

workshop should not be missed. It is essential to strike a balance between open reflection and practical planning.

To strengthen the impact of the workshops, it is advisable to connect this final reflection to the preparatory work done on local context and priorities. Organisers—especially those from key institutions such as local governments—should engage with relevant stakeholders in advance to explore how to carry forward the outcomes. This may include sharing results in appropriate forums, defining concrete follow-up actions, building on existing networks or platforms, and identifying opportunities for additional funding or support. Such proactive planning ensures the long-term relevance and integration of the workshop outcomes into ongoing local processes.

TIP: As an organiser, think ahead about potential actionable follow-ups that could emerge from the workshop. Examples include: integrating the scenarios into other planning or policy processes, presenting the results to the local food policy council, sharing key insights and action points with relevant stakeholders, developing communication materials to disseminate outcomes more broadly, or exploring opportunities for further collaboration and funding. Anticipating these possibilities can help ensure the workshop leads to meaningful, real-world impact.

2.3.5. Elaborating and Sharing the results: Resilient Transition Pathways

After the workshops, organisers should review, consolidate, and organise the outcomes of the process. This includes developing the resilient transition plans—ideally using a format like Table 6 (transition pathway)—ensuring that each entry is clearly articulated and accurately reflects the discussions and strategies proposed by participants.

It is also essential to compile detailed workshop minutes that document key points of discussion, group insights, and main takeaways. These minutes, along with the finalised resilient transition pathways, should be shared with all participants to provide a comprehensive record of the scenario planning process and its outcomes.

In addition, more accessible materials—such as summaries, infographics, or visual storytelling tools—can be created to communicate the results more widely. Sharing these with both participants and broader audiences helps extend the reach of the workshops and amplifies their impact beyond the event itself.

In **Barcelona**, organisers and facilitators developed the *Decalogue on Food Waste and the Right to Food* as part of the CULTIVATE project. In **Milan**, a

dedicated report was produced to capture key insights, practical tips, and lessons learned from the process. In **Utrecht**, the organisers and facilitators prepared a short report to send back to the participants. See Annex 5 to see all these documents.

General tips for the whole process

- **Keep it short, engaging, and focused.** Based on experiences in Milan, Utrecht, and Barcelona, each phase of the workshop should ideally last between 3.5 to 4 hours. This includes time for informal sharing and networking at the end, which helps strengthen relationships and sustain engagement.
- **Ensure diverse and balanced participation.** Aim for representation across key sectors—civil society, public institutions, and the private sector. Build on existing networks and contacts to identify participants, and follow up to confirm attendance and maintain commitment throughout the process.
- **Use visual aids to guide and inspire.** Visual prompts—such as large-format templates or posters—can help structure the sessions and make ideas easier to share. Graphic recording or live illustration can be particularly effective in visualising collective visions and transition pathways.
- **Don't underestimate the importance of preparation and follow-up.** Successfully engaging participants, developing meaningful materials, and processing outcomes in a way that leads to real impact all require significant time and attention. Invest in careful planning before the workshop and thoughtful dissemination afterward to ensure long-term value.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The development of the scenario planning workshops and the experiences in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht have offered valuable insights into how to plan more inclusive and resilient food sharing landscapes, which will contribute to building more just and resilient urban food systems. Below, we summarise the lessons learnt and reflect on the potential for broader applications of the results and the methodology.

First, the development of the scenario planning workshops highlighted the importance of **participation and diversity** in future-oriented planning. Co-creating a collective vision, designing transition pathways and stress-testing them served not only as strategic exercises but also as powerful moments of community-building, allowing stakeholders to share their perspectives on the future of the food-sharing landscape. Indeed, the commitment to adopt an inclusive approach – from the initial definition of the topic through to the design and facilitation of the workshops – enables a deeper understanding of the aspirations, concerns, and lived realities of those involved. It also fosters a shared capacity to navigate uncertainty. Moreover, this inclusivity lays the foundation for multi-sectoral engagement, empowering a wide range of actors to take coordinated action and encouraging an integrated approach to food system transformation.

While the workshop's design considered inclusivity criteria in terms of the process's what, who and how (see Box 1), there were limitations. Key actors engaged in the three city workshops, but some groups still remained underrepresented. A broader **inclusion** would have been possible with the participation of other actors directly or indirectly involved in the food sharing landscape. For example, Milan organisers report the lack of involvement of the citizens who benefit from the food waste recovery and redistribution activities or food security professionals. In Barcelona, there was no representation of the hospitality sector due to their limited capacity to attend the workshops during their work time. Although involving many and diverse actors increases the complexity of the workshops from the organisational side, it may offer a more comprehensive perspective on the food sharing landscape and its possible future configurations. It is relevant to consider if different spaces for participation need to be provided to ensure meaningful engagement, particularly of more excluded groups. In this regard, organisers should consider how the commitment and literacy required for the scenario planning workshops can be adjusted to broaden the potential participation. Not least, bureaucratic constraints linked to use of resources limited the capacity to remunerate participants or provide the resources necessary for their participation. Changing funding rules and

bureaucratic procedures is essential to ensure equitable spaces for more marginalised actors.

Second, the development of participatory scenario planning exercises can generate a wide range of **outcomes**. On one hand, they contribute to **building skills, capacities, and context-specific tools that can be transferred** to other settings, applied across sectors, or integrated into related planning processes—whether within public administration or specific community-led initiatives. For example, the scenarios developed in each city can be used by various organisations to create and stress-test their plans and strategies. Participants also reported gaining valuable planning skills—such as backcasting—that they can apply professionally. On the other hand, the transition pathways—both in their initial and stress-tested forms—provide **actionable plans for policymakers and local stakeholders**. These outputs serve as valuable resources for informing policy development, guiding advocacy efforts, and supporting accountability in the pursuit of more sustainable and equitable food systems.

Thirdly, the scenario planning process offers **valuable tools for decision-making and advocacy**. The outputs obtained allow identifying potential pathways and anticipating emerging trends, thereby **empowering decision-makers to develop more adaptive and forward-looking strategies**. Moreover, the active participation of local administrations in the scenario planning workshops can help strengthen political commitment and increase the likelihood that the collective visions and transition pathways will be integrated into future formal strategies and policy frameworks. For example, the Municipality of Milan has expressed interest in aligning the workshop results with its Climate Action Plan. In Barcelona, the local administration developed a *Decalogue on Food Waste and the Right to Food* (see Annex 4), directly informed by the scenario planning process. Additionally, the workshop outcomes were presented at a regional event co-organised by the Catalan government, which focused on food waste redistribution initiatives. Food sharing initiatives can also use the resilient transition pathways as **advocacy tools to push for new local policies and strategies**, while better anticipating social, economic, and environmental changes. These pathways support more informed, agile responses and operational adjustments. To maximise their impact, it is essential that the scenario planning workshops are embedded within the local policy agenda and have the support and buy-in of key stakeholders. Notably, the scenarios also revealed the importance of **fostering creative capacity across public, private, and social sectors**—especially in light of potential shifts in the power dynamics among

these actors. For instance, some scenarios imagined futures where the public sector had weakened or disappeared entirely, or where private interests dominated the food system. These insights underscore the value of maintaining flexibility and adaptability. Ultimately, the scenario planning outcomes should not be seen as fixed endpoints, but as springboards for ongoing reflection and evolution—helping ensure that local plans remain relevant, inclusive, and responsive to changing realities.

Finally, the scenario planning workshops presented in this guidebook are both **transferable and adaptable** to fields beyond food sharing and the broader food system domain. By tailoring the participatory approach, a wide range of sectors and territorial contexts can benefit from deeper stakeholder engagement and improved responsiveness to complex, evolving challenges. Creating sustainable, resilient, and just environments—whether rural, peri-urban, or urban—requires multi-actor collaboration and cross-sectoral integration. The experience in Utrecht, where food governance intersected with climate policy, provides a compelling example of how such integration can be achieved in practice.

In conclusion, this guidebook offers a comprehensive framework for urban food sharing while also presenting a flexible, replicable model for participatory planning and sustainable development across diverse policy areas and geographic contexts.

4. METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

The food system is at the heart of current social and environmental global challenges. Cities play a crucial role in shaping these challenges as well as the food system and, therefore, driving its potential transformation (Davies & Evans, 2019; Jackson et al., 2021; HLPE, 2024). In the last decade, food sharing initiatives are becoming more prevalent in cities, offering new opportunities to shape more sustainable urban food systems (Davies et al., 2019, 2017). Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) are collaborative practices conducted by formal or informal organisations to grow, cook, eat, or distribute food and share food-related skills, knowledge, spaces, and/or tools (Davies, 2014, 2019). These initiatives include activities in areas such as food waste recovery and redistribution, collective growing in urban gardens, community cooking and eating together. The environmental and social benefits of FSIs are increasingly recognised in the literature (Davies et al., 2019, 2017; Herrero & Moragues-Faus, 2024). However, there is still a need to better understand how they can be supported to maximise their positive impact, which is one of the aims of the CULTIVATE. Specifically, WP4 deals with governance and includes as objectives to improve understanding of how policy and regulation affect urban and peri urban FSIs, and to co-produce knowledge on how to transform existing regulatory regimes, governance structures and habits in order to prevent and reduce food waste and promote sustainable food sharing.

For that purpose, we have conducted three interrelated tasks. First, we conducted a literature review on food sharing governance to understand the enablers and barriers affecting FSI (see related policy brief in Herrero & Moragues-Faus, 2024). Secondly, an analysis of the governance landscape affecting food waste and redistribution, urban food growing, and the social and solidarity food economy of the three Hub cities participating in the project: Milan (IT) (Matteini et al., 2024), Utrecht (NL) (Medema et al., 2024), and Barcelona (SP) (Herrero et al., 2024). Finally, we have designed and applied participative future scenario workshops to co-produce actionable plans that promote sustainable food sharing in the three hub cities. The design of the workshops is presented in this guide, as well as the key lessons learned from their application in Barcelona, Milan and Utrecht. To design the workshops, we built on existing literature on futuring exercises, as explained below.

Futuring exercises have become important tools in research and planning, offering structured approaches to explore possibilities, challenge assumptions, and incorporate diverse perspectives in shaping sustainable and just configurations

(Fitzgerald & Davies, 2022; Hebinck et al., 2022; Muiderman et al., 2020; Fergnani, 2019). Defined as “systematically thinking about the future” (Tussyadiah & Miller, 2020, p. 676), futuring helps address complex challenges such as urban food system sustainability (Fitzgerald & Davies, 2022, 2024). It enables researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to consider multiple interconnected factors and assess potential outcomes (Hebinck et al., 2022).

The literature shows that futuring can take very diverse forms, providing a diversity of insights and potential benefits. For example, co-created future scenarios can reveal new strategies, challenge dominant assumptions, and promote more inclusive and democratic decision-making. Such exercises can give voice to a wider diversity of perspectives and allow for the anticipation of actions that advance long-term objectives amid uncertain futures (Muiderman et al., 2020; Vervoort & Gupta, 2018). They also can help identify pathways for sustainability transformations and support the development of strategic insights involving diverse stakeholders (Hebinck et al., 2022). By exploring alternative scenarios, these tools foster a deeper understanding of present systems and critically examine existing policies, engaging policymakers more directly with potential futures (Hebinck et al., 2022; Fitzgerald & Davies, 2022, 2024).

There is a wide range of participatory methods and tools employed in futuring exercises, such as visioning, backcasting, and imaging. These futuring exercises can promote reflexivity about different ways of engaging with both desirable and unexpected scenarios. They also foster future literacy, that is, the ability to understand, imagine, and act on diverse futures. The potential benefits and shortcomings of futuring depend on how these exercises are conceptualised, designed, and implemented.

Academics have developed different classifications to understand the diversity of futuring exercises in terms of the conceptualisation. For example, Fitzgerald and Davies (2022) identify three clusters of futuring practices according to the different ways of thinking about, imagining and shaping the future, particularly in the context of sustainability transitions. *Corporate Foresight* practices primarily generate actionable insights, focusing on developing strategies and often commercial products. This approach typically involves a limited number of elite professionals driven by techno-optimism and focusing on maintaining market advantage (p. 3). *Environmental Future* practices are driven by concerns about escalating resource use and the resulting climate and biodiversity crises, primarily through future-oriented environmental governance. These practices rely on environmental

modelling and anticipatory foresight approaches and assume a need for technological and managerial solutions (p. 3). *Humanity at the Limen* explores how humanity can transition to more sustainable futures, particularly by addressing complex issues. These practices emphasise systemic change, diverse worldviews, and critical reflection, using novel engagement methods to explore alternative futures that focus on social and cultural dimensions (pp. 3–4).

Another classification is provided by Hebinck et al. (2022) who identify four archetypal approaches to engaging with the future. These approaches represent different ways of systematically thinking about the future and how it relates to the current situation. *Probable future* approaches lie in the field of predictive processes, which is mainly connected to risk mitigation, linear planning, and quantitative modelling. *Plausible future* approaches focus instead on a range of possible scenarios without trying to predict a specific one. This approach is used to stress test plans and visions to identify potential challenges and unexpected events. *Pluralistic future* approaches see futures as a combination of different societal groups with different desires and ambitions. These approaches often develop step plans to reach desirable scenarios and/or visions resulting from a backcasting process. *Performative future* approaches aim to critically examine the ideas about the future embedded in societies. These approaches are less strategically oriented but help critique the dominant narratives about the future, opening new spaces for more inclusive and democratic imagining (Hebinck et al., 2022, pp. 414-415).

According to Fitzgerald and Davies (2022), futuring exercise that engage with food sharing initiatives to maximise their positive impacts on urban food systems should be rooted in the practice of *Humanity at the Limen* (limen defined as the state of being in the threshold between one recognised state and the other). This practice suggests “dramatic changes in the balance of power, questions the upper boundaries of demographic increases and economic progress, proposes alternatives to the capitalistic system” (Fergnani, 2019, p. 113). *Humanity at the Limen* explores how humanity can transition to more sustainable futures, particularly by addressing complex issues. Within this framework, the exercise can explore and emphasise diverse perspectives, cultures, values and initiatives to create alternative narratives of the current systems. These practices emphasise systemic change, diverse worldviews, and critical reflection, using novel engagement methods to explore alternative futures that focus on social and cultural dimensions (Fitzgerald & Davies, 2022, pp.3-4). Indeed, this framework seems to align with the nature of FSIs, which are often driven by community values, sustainability, and social justice (Davies et al., 2019, 2017; Davies, 2019) and have

hybrid governance structures (Manganelli, 2024; Moragues-Faus et al., 2022; Verbruggen & Havinga, 2017). Mobilising *Humanity at the Limen* practice in futuring exercises can be combined with different types of futuring exercises as defined by Hebinck et al (2022).

The research of Hebinck et al. (2022) suggest that a combination of *pluralistic* and *plausible approaches*, with a strong emphasis on inclusivity and reflexivity as the most effective for informing governance changes. In the context of CULTIVATE, a pluralistic approach is crucial for food sharing planning because it centres on creating desired visions that reflect the values and ambitions of the groups involved in food sharing. This approach considers that different stakeholders have distinct objectives, motivations, and future visions. It encourages the creation of a shared vision through a participatory process, which is then activated and translated into action through the co-development of transition pathways through backcasting techniques. In addition, a *plausible future approach* is also highly valuable because it acknowledges the complexity of food systems and the uncertainties of future configurations. This approach promotes the exploration of scenarios that serve to stress test the plans and adaptive capacities of FSIs. These exploratory scenarios envision unexpected social, economic, political, and cultural changes that could challenge the vision established through a pluralistic approach as well as the transition pathways developed in a mindset of business as usual. Consequently, plausible or explorative scenarios can be used to review backcasting processes, acting as a stress test to enhance and adapt the initial transition pathway to unpredictable changes, making these plans more resilient.

Building on this literature, in CULTIVATE we have developed a process rooted in the practice of *Humanity at the Limen* and therefore engaged diverse actors in critically thinking and planning together for systemic change. The methods employed mobilised a *pluralistic* approach, by co-producing a desired shared vision for sustainable food sharing in specific cities, and a *plausible* approach by using exploratory scenarios to stress test plans to achieve that common vision.

For that purpose, we used existing plausible scenarios developed in the framework of the [European project TRANSMANGO](#), which aimed to explore diverse transition pathways to a sustainable and food secure food system. This project developed sets of plausible scenarios for the European Food System and a scenario-guided transition pathways methodology which provides an operational approach to assist stakeholders in decision-making and building resilient food systems (Vervoort et al., 2014, 2016a, 2016b). We mobilised the TRANSMANGO scenarios because they

provide a common framework for Europe; scenario skeletons that can be adapted to different contexts, times and socio-ecological changes; and a diversity within scenario sets which maximises challenges to the current situation. They have also been tested widely at the European and local level, in the context of food system transformation and mobilised in a participatory fashion that matches CULTIVATE's needs. However, this guide could also be used mobilising other sets of plausible scenarios if needed.

In summary, this guide builds on recent literature on futuring exercises and successful experiences to develop a guide that combines pluralistic, plausible and Human at the limen approaches to co-produce knowledge and plans on how to promote sustainable food sharing. Section 2, explain step by step the different tools mobilised as well as tips and insights from their application in the Hub cities.

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6. ANNEXES

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Annex 1 – Tarot-inspired visuals created as part of the scenario planning process in Barcelona, designed to enrich and support future workshop exercises

Annex 2 - Example of the step outline for the Phase 1 in Barcelona

DURATION	TIME	WHERE	BLOCK	ACTION	WHO DOES IT	MATERIAL NEEDS/ WHO PROVIDES	COMMENTS
-	04/04/24	-	Previous to Workshop 1	Send questions + reminder + agenda?	Amaranta writes + Gunilla sends		This needs to be sent with a reminder of the workshops and an explanation about the catering.
30 minutes	Day of workshop at 9:00	Torre Jussana (all the spaces)	Previous to Workshop 1	Prepare the spaces (space for meeting + welcoming/catering space)	Amaranta, Gunilla, Ana, Giulio	Tables/Torre Jussana Post-its, & pens/PEMB	
30 minutes	9:30-10:00	Entrance	Welcoming	Provide coffee/tea	Catering service	cups/Catering service	
30 minutes	9:30-10:00	Entrance	Welcoming	Registration	Gunilla + Giulio	List of attendants + stickers to put names by colour + consent form/Gunilla	They need to sign a document to ensure we can use the pictures and the recording. They also need to write their names + organisation on a sticker.
30 minutes	10:00-10:30	Main room (together)	Introduction	Presentation of the workshops and activities	Ana	Screen/Torre Jussana	
30 minutes	10:30-11:00	Main room (split)	Visioning	Visualisation of a desirable future	Four facilitators, one in each group:	Big papers, pens, stickers	Recording is important. Facilitators are in charge of the recording.
30 minutes	11:00-11:30	Main room (together)	Visioning	Sharing the visioning	Ana	Board / Torre Jussana	All visions are taped to the walls by facilitators, and the whole participant group visits vision by vision, and we extract the common and conflicted elements.
15 minutes	11:30-11:45	-	Break	Break	-	-	
60 minutes	11:45-12:45	Main room (split)	Back-casting	First back-casting	4 facilitators, one in each group:	Big papers, pens	
15 minutes	12:45-13:00	Main room (together)	Feedback and close	Listen to the groups' feedback + closure	Ana		
30 minutes	13:00-14:00	Outside	Light meal	Networking			

Annex 3 - Example of participants planning for one of the goals backcasted in Phase 1, which has been converted into a Table

GOAL: Barcelona has multiple approaches to guaranteeing the right to food, through multiple organizations and programs. Universal basic income has been introduced in order to fight different “poverties” at the same time. Furthermore, this has been done by incorporating the reuse of food loss and waste.			
Sub-Goals	A universal basic income system is being developed that can guarantee access to basic resources, empowering the individual and based on freedom of choice, and abandoning the discourse of the fragmentation of poverty.	A social consensus is created in favour of guaranteeing healthy and sustainable food and in favour of the defragmentation of poverty	Food recovery options are included
Step 1		Social entities are putting pressure to create a centrality of the discourse on food. Clear diagnoses and infographics are being carried out on the problem posed by food poverty as well as the impact on health and human development. Collaboration with research centers that can analyze and give context to data from the administration and entities that work for food security.	The discourses on the importance of not individualizing the problem of food poverty are worked on but rather focusing on the functioning of the system, how migration dynamics and the lack of social and family networks influence it and how they can work together.
Step 2		From the entities that fight against poverty and from the experience of the administration, discourses are created on the defragmentation of poverty: We should not work to alleviate the different types of poverty (housing, food, health...) but rather create mechanisms that combat them all at the same time, while regulating the goods of greatest need.	
Step 3		A social consensus is being reached on the universalization of the right to a healthy and sustainable diet. This means that the	This country model on food captures the unsustainability of food losses due to market

		administration and politicians have a model of a country in food where this right is recognized and care is taken to create the conditions for the production and accessibility of local and sustainable products.	frictions/aesthetic criteria and seeks solutions.
Step 4	Large-scale pilot tests are being carried out on the operation of guaranteed basic incomes that allow access to food as well as other basic goods.	In combination with the basic income pilot tests, policies and initiatives by citizens or social entities are carried out to guarantee the supply and consumption of healthy and sustainable products for all citizens.	
Step 5		The operation of these basic incomes and the results they have are disseminated to raise awareness among citizens and the administration of the benefits and needs of this measure.	
Step 6		L'administració, tot i que garantint la llibertat d'elecció, segueix fomentant determinants models de consum més desitjables a través de l'educació, incentius econòmics, models de distribució...	
Step 7	There is a regulated and functioning guaranteed income that empowers citizens and allows them to access all basic goods, defragmenting poverty and guaranteeing the individual's freedom of choice. In general, individuals have more decision-making capacity and can be more aware of the importance of adequate nutrition, and take measures in this regard.		

Step 8			Zero waste can never be achieved, so there will continue to be initiatives that must ensure that this waste can be channeled while helping to guarantee food for all citizens.
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Annex 4 – Summary of the two sets of TRANSMANGO European Future Scenarios .

	Fed up Europe	Retrotopia	The Protein Union	The Price of Health
Consumption Patterns	High animal products, high sugar/processed food (unhealthy meat eaters)	Low animal products, high sugar/processed food (unhealthy vegans and vegetarians)	Meat consumption, low sugar/processed food: strong innovation on animal proteins - insects	Low animal products, low sugar/processed food (healthy vegans and vegetarians)
Environmental Degradation	Biodiversity loss, water pollution, soil degradation etc. Continued environmental decline	Environmental degradation is reversed	Environment is stabilised but at lower levels than today	Environment is stabilised
Poverty & Economic Inequality	Low poverty high inequality – few are truly poor, but some are extremely	Low poverty, low inequality	High poverty, low inequality – people have less assets but strong state support.	High poverty, high inequality -incomes are low, but quality of life has been decoupled from income through other means of subsistence. The rich lead very different lives.
Social & Technical Innovation	Low innovation, private sector driven: Public and private sectors are inert.	High innovation, public sector driven	High innovation, public sector driven: The public sector stimulates innovation, but there is an important role for the private sector	High innovation, needs driven, bottom-up: local initiatives, local businesses and local governments
Urban & Rural Population Dynamics	Increase in both urban and rural populations	Decrease in both urban and rural populations	Decrease in rural, increase in urban	Increase in rural decrease in urban
Power & Market Concentration	Extreme concentration: several companies	Healthy competition exists in all sectors:	Some sectors dominated by a few global players; others less concentrated	Extreme decentralisation dominated by SMEs

	dominate the entire market worldwide	significant role for SMEs		
Trade Agreements	Free markets (more free trade agreements, removal of subsidisation)	Protected markets (less free trade more subsidies)	Protected markets (less free trade more subsidies)	Protected markets (less free trade more subsidies)
Resource Use	Resource crisis	Significant reduction in resource use/demand	Resource scarcity	Significant reduction in resource use/demand

Table 4 - The first set of TRANSMANGO Scenarios. Source: (Deppermann et al. 2015, p. 14)

	The Gravy Train	Goodbye to All That	Too busy to cook	The Grass is Greener
Consumption Patterns	High animal products, high sugar/processed food (unhealthy meat eaters)	Low animal products, high sugar/processed food (unhealthy vegans and vegetarians)	Low animal products, high sugar/processed food (unhealthy vegans and vegetarians)	Low animal products, low sugar/processed food (healthy vegans and vegetarians)
Environmental Degradation	Biodiversity loss, water pollution, soil degradation etc. Continued environmental decline	Biodiversity loss, water pollution, soil degradation etc. Continued environmental decline	Environment is revived	Environment is stabilized worldwide but at lower levels than today
Poverty & Economic Inequality	Low poverty, high inequality	High poverty, high inequality	Low poverty, high inequality	High poverty, high inequality

Social & Technical Innovation	High innovation, bottom up and needs driven	Low innovation, private sector driven	High innovation, private sector driven	Low innovation, private sector driven
Urban & Rural Population Dynamics	Rural and urban Populations stabilized	Reruralisation	Rural and urban Populations stabilized	Decrease in urban and rural populations
Power & Market Concentration	Extreme decentralisation, dominated by SMEs	Some sectors dominated by a few global players, others less concentrated	Extreme decentralisation, dominated by SMEs	Competitive markets, mix of larger and smaller companies
Trade Agreements	Protected markets (less free trade more subsidies)	Protected markets (less free trade more subsidies)	Free markets (more free trade agreements, removal of subsidisation)	Free markets (more free trade agreements, removal of subsidisation)
Resource Use	Resource scarcity	Resource scarcity	Decoupled economies	Resource scarcity

Table 5 - The second set of TRANSMANGO Scenarios. Source: (Deppermann et al. 2015, p. 16)

Annex 5 – Documents prepared by organisers and facilitators to summarise the key takeaways from the scenario planning workshops held in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht

Decalogue on Food Waste and the Right to Food within the CULTIVATE Project (Barcelona)

Introduction

The CULTIVATE project is part of the Horizon Europe program and aims to generate knowledge about shared food initiatives in urban and peri-urban environments to promote more sustainable food systems. In Barcelona, scenario planning workshops were organized, focusing on the dual challenge of reducing food waste and ensuring the right to healthy food.

This document summarizes the results of two workshops held on April 16 and May 28, 2024, which served to imagine possible futures, develop strategies to address potential uncertainties and challenges, and improve the planning and resilience of the participating initiatives and institutions. Through a methodology based on future scenarios and back-casting, barriers and enabling factors were identified, as well as a set of concrete actions to be considered.

Methodology

The workshops followed a participatory methodology structured in several phases:

- **Creating a shared vision (2040):** Participants defined what they would like the food system to look like in the long term.
- **Identifying key actions:** Using the back-casting technique, necessary actions to achieve this vision were defined.
- **Analyzing future scenarios:** Three scenarios were used to test the robustness of the proposed actions:
 - *Europe is fed up* (climate and social crisis, regression in sustainability policies).
 - *Retrotopia* (high technological development and state control, but inequality in social integration).
 - *The price of health* (migration from rural to urban areas and sustainable diets as a necessity).

Decalogue of Conclusions and Action Lines

1. Food governance requires greater coordination and inclusion

Food policies require the involvement of multiple actors, from public administrations to businesses, social organizations, and consumers. The

workshops highlighted the importance of a more structured governance framework, where different stakeholders in the food system can collaborate effectively. The need for greater coordination between public administrations, social entities, and the private sector was identified to ensure the implementation of policies that prevent food waste and guarantee the right to food. Participants also proposed the creation of a dedicated governmental body to work across sectors to address these challenges.

2. Food must be considered a right, not just a market commodity

Workshops participants emphasized that access to healthy and sustainable food is essential for public well-being and must be ensured beyond market logic. The current model prioritizes economic profitability over food equity, which can create significant inequalities in accessing quality food. To counter this trend, initiatives such as a Guaranteed Food Income have been proposed to ensure that everyone has access to nutritious food.

3. Localizing the food system can enhance sustainability

Food systems based on long supply chains and global markets are vulnerable to economic, political, or environmental crises, as seen in recent years. The workshops highlighted that planning production based on population needs can help reduce food losses at the source and improve system efficiency. Strengthening local farming through land banks, support services, and mechanisms that ensure farm profitability was proposed. Additionally, the creation of a public platform to facilitate the commercialization of local and organic products was valued.

4. Tax policies can play a key role in transforming the food system

The current tax system does not always favor the consumption of sustainable food nor penalize environmentally harmful practices. To make sustainable food more competitive, fiscal incentives were proposed, such as reduced VAT for healthy and sustainable products. At the same time, measures like taxing food waste through specific levies were suggested to discourage wasteful practices.

5. Technology can help optimize food waste management

The integration of innovative, responsible, and low-impact technologies can improve the management of food surpluses and reduce losses throughout the supply chain. One of the explored scenarios suggested the use of agricultural drones and other digital tools to optimize food production and distribution. The development of technological systems to facilitate food traceability and redistribution was also considered.

6. Education and information are essential for changing consumption habits

The workshops emphasized the importance of incorporating food education into school curricula to promote healthy diets and reduce food waste. Improving public

communication on the environmental and social impact of food losses, as well as providing clear and reliable information to citizens, was also proposed.

7. Food waste indicators should include social and environmental dimensions

Currently, food waste is mainly measured in terms of discarded food volume. Participants noted that this information should be complemented with indicators reflecting social and environmental impacts, such as the correlation between food waste and food poverty or the CO₂ emissions associated with food production and disposal.

8. Social and solidarity economy initiatives can play a key role in food redistribution

The workshops highlighted the role of social organizations in recovering and redistributing food and emphasized the need to strengthen their operational capacity through funding mechanisms and institutional support. Improving coordination among these initiatives was also proposed to optimize available resources and ensure more efficient distribution.

9. Food waste legislation requires more effective implementation

Although laws have been passed in recent years to reduce food waste, their enforcement remains uneven and, in some cases, ineffective. Participants identified the need to strengthen control and inspection mechanisms and to allocate adequate budgets to food waste prevention and recovery policies.

10. Diversifying the food system can enhance resilience

The scenarios explored in the workshops revealed different possible evolutions of the food system, highlighting the importance of promoting mixed models that integrate technology, small-scale local farming, agroecology, and more decentralized production and distribution systems. Initiatives such as urban gardens, self-production of food, and exchange networks can help make the food system more flexible and resilient in the face of future uncertainties.

Final Reflections

The proposals emerging from the CULTIVATE workshops suggest a transition towards a more sustainable, equitable, and adaptive food model. However, moving in this direction requires a collective commitment that includes governments, the private sector, and civil society.

This decalogue does not aim to provide definitive answers but serves as a starting point for reflection and to foster debate on how to address food waste and ensure the right to food in a future marked by multiple uncertainties.

Scenario planning workshop in Milan. Lessons Learnt and Tips

Organisational Considerations

- Challenges with participant availability. Gathering participants required time, as potential participants often faced scheduling conflicts. Many participants expressed limited availability, highlighting the need to optimise sessions to accommodate their busy schedules.
- Group speaker mechanism. During the workshop, each group selected a *speaker* from the participants, a person who presented the group's results during the plenary sessions. The other participants could as well participate in the discussion by supporting the speaker or adding their contribution. This approach helped shorten the time and keep the discussion organised.
- Time constraints. Time emerged as a significant constraint:
- Some participants had to leave early, disrupting the flow and limiting their full involvement.
- Although reports can be sent to absent participants, it is not equivalent to their real-time participation.
- Participants from the private sector, such as CEOs, often faced interruptions (e.g., phone calls), detracting from their engagement.
- Use of municipal premises. The decision to host the sessions in municipal premises instead of a “neutral environment” had mixed outcomes:
 - *Positive*: The setting lent credibility to the event, encouraging attendance.
 - *Negative*: Initially, participants were cautious due to the formal nature of the venue. However, they relaxed as the session progressed, highlighting the importance of creating a welcoming environment.

Methodological Considerations

- Terminology clarity. The concepts of “vision” and “scenarios” were found to be potentially confusing. Greater emphasis should be placed on clarifying these terms to avoid misunderstandings and ensure alignment. Facilitators suggest using “vision” in Phase 1 to describe the desirable future and avoid using “scenario,” which should refer to the downscaled narration of the TRANSMANGO Scenarios.
- Informal approach to discussing formal topics. An informal approach was employed to encourage participants to engage with formal issues.

This strategy effectively facilitated open dialogue and easing participants into discussions about complex topics.

- Visibilisation of visions and ideas often hidden. Facilitators recognised that the workshops offered to explore the perspectives and desires of the stakeholders on the topic. The workshops were the place for radical thinking, to discuss these visions and desires collectively among stakeholders from the public and private sectors and civil society.
- Avoid fixation on specific ideas. Participants often fixate on certain ideas and visions, potentially stifling creativity and alternative viewpoints. Strategies should be employed to encourage exploration beyond initial ideas.
- Avoid participation fatigue. There is a risk of overburdening participants, which can lead to "participation fatigue." Care should be taken to manage the frequency and intensity of involvement to maintain participant enthusiasm and engagement.
- Clustering process. As facilitators reported, clustering the visions was the most challenging part. Reducing the ideas and desires that emerged from the four groups into three or five topics was perceived as messy and opened a debate between participants and facilitators on how to cluster the ideas and desires. Having a clearer structure and/or guide would reduce timing and facilitate this step.
- Assign more than one vision during the stress-test. During the stress-test in the second workshop, the number of participants did not allow the organisation of more than 2 groups. To each group, facilitators assigned two transition pathways and the related explorative downscaled scenarios.

Future Applications

There is an intention to refine and streamline the methodology for future use. This will ensure better manageability and adaptability, allowing broader and more effective implementation.

Facilitators reported a positive reception from the participants in Milan, including academics and other private and public stakeholders, who expressed a willingness to use this approach again.

Moreover, Milan City Council is interested in using the methodology for developing the municipal Piano Aria Clima (the plan for improving air quality and environmental conditions), indicating its value and relevance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The scenario planning workshops were a great opportunity for food sharing initiatives to think about a long-term perspective, an exercise they rarely do. They

were the occasion for radical thinking to emerge, to explore hidden or underestimated ideas and visions of the different stakeholders involved.

The Milan session provided valuable insights into the strengths and challenges of the current methodology. Key recommendations include:

- Streamlining processes to address time constraints and participant availability.
- Enhancing clarity in terminology and methodology to prevent confusion.
- For the stress testing process, facilitators should assign the TRANSMANGO scenario beforehand to stress-test the transition pathway to optimise timing.
- Creating an environment that fosters creativity while avoiding fixation on initial ideas.
- Balancing the benefits and drawbacks of formal venues to ensure participant comfort and engagement.
- Refining feedback mechanisms to capture a broader range of perspectives.
- Considering doing the two phases in one day.

These adjustments will help improve the effectiveness and ensure its successful application in future sessions.

Conclusions from the final report prepared by the organizers and facilitators in Utrecht

1. Food Governance requires more coordination and inclusion

City-level food policy. The workshops emphasized the importance of a more structured governance framework, in which different stakeholders in the food system can work together effectively.

There is a need for more coordination between government departments to give food a prominent place in the city agenda. Especially when it comes to the policy “Healthy Urban living strategy”, among others. Participants also suggested setting up a special government body that works across sectors to address these challenges.

2. Education and information are essential to improving our food environment

The workshops emphasized the importance of including food education in both school curricula and in all types of company canteens, restaurants and community kitchens. Participants suggested setting up a TASK-FORCE to share more knowledge about sustainable and healthy food across all levels of society. Improving public communication about the environmental and social impact of food, as well as providing clear and reliable information to citizens, was also proposed. Every school has a vegetable garden and food grows in the city.

3. The Peaceful City

The possible aging of our population and the loneliness that can be linked to it and the fear that can arise from the polarizing society that is becoming increasingly racist is a very important challenge in the city. Food and education can be a social bonding agent to ensure that Utrecht remains a Peaceful City. Social brokerage is very important! Governments and food grassroots initiatives, social designers, and residents learn together to deal with conflict and polarization. How do we create more time between all layers of society?

4. Initiatives for social and solidarity economy can play an important role in the redistribution of food, which unites as a cooperative form to set up, for example, outdoor kitchens or local supermarkets.

The workshops emphasized the role of cooperatives in bringing the food chain into the hands of the residents of Utrecht and generating alternative economic means to provide everyone with healthy and sustainable food. More ownership in deciding

how food is produced, consumed and delivered to you brings people together and prevents loneliness and mistrust.

Operational capacity needs to be strengthened through financing mechanisms and institutional support. Improving coordination between these initiatives was also suggested to optimize available resources and ensure more efficient distribution.

5. Diversification of the food system can increase resilience

The scenarios explored in the workshops revealed different possible evolutions of the food system and emphasized the importance of promoting mixed models that integrate nature-inclusive food production, local distribution systems, urban gardens and self-production to make the food system more flexible and resilient in the face of future uncertainties.

6. Space around the city is used much better for nature-inclusive food production, recreation and housing. In this way, there is an abundance of healthy, locally produced and sustainable food within reach of every Utrecht resident, regardless of the residents' income.

The workshops emphasized the importance of laws such as VAB (vacant agricultural development) that need to be improved to enable, for example, living on farms, or DLG, for a better rural area and spatial design. Less Natura2000 but more natural quality, fewer rules and more self-management by cooperatives as “our country”, among other things.

7. Plant-based lifestyle does not feel like a compulsion, but a pleasure! Right to healthy food for everyone!

The workshop emphasized that healthy meals should be available everywhere, which also means less or no meat. Beans, nuts and seaweed are central to the diet as a source of protein instead of meat. Everyone participates, chefs, governments and food initiatives. The development of "the healthy and vegan company canteen" is mentioned more often. The story behind the food on your plate is very important to provide both government institutions and private companies and other organizations with healthier meals.

8. Tax policy can play a key role in transforming the food system

To make sustainable food more affordable, fiscal incentives are proposed, such as a reduced VAT for healthy and sustainable products. Food should be seen as a right, not just as a market product. Workshop participants emphasized that access to

healthy and sustainable food is essential for the well-being of urban residents and its affordability must be ensured, beyond market logic.

In short:

The proposals that emerged from the CULTIVATE workshops suggest a transition to a more sustainable, fair and adaptive food model. However, moving in this direction requires a collective commitment that includes governments, the private sector and civil society.

These conclusions are not intended to provide definitive answers, but serve as a starting point for reflection and to stimulate debate on how diverse parties in Utrecht can jointly create an inclusive, future-proof and sustainable food environment in a future that is characterized by multiple uncertainties.

